
**MODERN METHODS OF TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL TRAINING IN
TABLE TENNIS LESSONS**
**СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ТЕХНИКО-ТАКТИЧЕСКОЙ
ПОДГОТОВКЕ НА УРОКАХ НАСТОЛЬНОГО ТЕННИСА**

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Annotation: this article describes table tennis and its techniques and methods of teaching it. Also, in table tennis, the methods of introducing the ball into the game, the methods of protection are described in detail.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассказывается о настольном теннисе и его технике, а также о методах его обучения. Также в настольном теннисе описаны способы ввода мяча в игру, способы защиты.

Keywords: Sports, Sports, National Sports Games, National Games, tennis, stages of development, racket, technique, tactics.

Ключевые слова: Спорт, Спорт, национальные спортивные игры, национальные игры, теннис, этапы развития, ракетка, техника, тактика.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev and the leadership of our state, there is a constant emphasis on physical education and sports. In particular, in the decrees and resolutions of June 3, 2017, PQ – 3031 “on measures for the further development of Physical Education and mass sports”, March 5, 2018, PF-5368 “on measures for the radical improvement of the public administration system in the field of Physical Education and sports”, issues related to improving the health of the population of our country.

Physical education and sports are of great importance in strengthening the health of young people in our country, increasing the level of physical fitness, improving the protection of the motherland and improving the ability to work. Physical education and sports are considered the main tools in the comprehensive physical development of people.

Table tennis has two ways to return a ball by hitting it with a racket. The first is to direct the racket. In this case, it is impossible to know in advance how the ball will move. This method is used by most novice players. The type of rotation depends on the angle of the racket and the direction of movement at the time of contact with the ball. There are several types of ball stroke, the main ones are nakat, podrezka and top

– spin. In order to succeed in table tennis, it is necessary to master various methods of ball-beating and be able to apply them when rolling a ball.

From the right, nakat is one of the main methods of attack. In this case, the racket moves up and forward and hits the top side of the ball. The procedure for hitting the ball is as follows: the legs are shoulder-width apart, the knees are slightly bent. The left leg is placed slightly forward. The body weight is divided into both legs in one rhythm. The upper part of the body is bent slightly left to the table side, the hand holding the racket is extended back for the blow. The arm held by the racket moves when the legs, racket and the approaching ball form an equilateral triangle. The ball is hit when it hits the table, jumps, reaches the highest point, and the hand holding the racket returns left-to-top. When the racket hits the ball, the shoulder part of the hand moves forward from the ball. The racket moves in The Shape of an arc, slowly changing the angle of inclination, and as a result, turning the ball from the top occurs. The palm of the hand rotates the ball with a quick movement. At the time of the blow, the body weight goes to the left leg. After the blow, it is necessary to quickly return to the previous position

The purpose of this shock method is to achieve a strong rotation of the ball from the top. It is performed at great speed, thus making it difficult for the opponent to return the shot. First, it is unexpected every time the ball touches the table and jumps. Secondly, the ball received by the racket may also not obey, so moving it in the desired direction is very and very complicated. The good thing about Top-Spin is that a ball hit by a spin flies high over the net and gives the player who hits the shot an advantage. It is believed that Top - spin can always be applied, but this is not the case. A wide and powerful shot is delivered with a hand extended in the Top spin. Levelling the arm at the start of the movement provides the opportunity to increase the speed of the racket and the impact with the palm and shoulder parts of the hand. In contrast to the Nakat shot, hand movement in top spin is directed to the top, while striking the ball is in a sliding fashion. Starting position: the left leg is placed slightly forward, the right arm is straightened from the right side to the back. The body is tilted to the right to enhance the impact. The knees are bent, the body is in a calm state. The Top spin begins with a quick move to the hit side. The right hand moves forward-left-upward. The body weight is transferred from the right foot to the left foot. As a result of inertia, the body and arm can go to the left. When hitting the ball, it is necessary for the racket to slip out of it. The force of the ball hitting the racket in this case is very low. But the palm of the hand gives him the last acceleration. There is also a right-hand variant of top-Spin, called side-top-spin. The difference between a straight top-spin and a side-top-spin is that the hand held by the racket is directed from the side to the ball, lowering the palm of the hand more down

The movement of the ball is just like the right side nakati. The spins required for the ball are performed with a top-forward motion. The sequence of the blow is as follows: the legs are shoulder-width apart, slightly bent, the left leg is slightly forward, the body weight is divided into both legs in one stroke. The arm is bent at waist height from the elbow and directed back and left, the shoulder part of the arm is parallel to the table level. When hit, the shoulder part of the hand moves rapidly forward, the racket touches the ball from the top, after which the hand freely returns to the right-top. The center of gravity moves to the right leg, the arm returns to the initial position.

Left-hand top-spin is used less frequently than right-hand top-spin. The traditional type of Top-Spin is not used on the left side, this is explained by the need to strengthen the blow, since in this case, in addition to spinning from the top, a side spin also occurs.

To perform an open racket podrezka, it is necessary to hit the racket from top to bottom on the ball. After the podrezka, the ball rises to the top, so the faster the ball rotates, the farther it flies. Podrezka is a defensive shot. It is complicated to hit the ball that is coming with the Podrezka. The player looks almost straight at the table in the initial position, with the left foot slightly forward, the hand moving back-to-top first and then back-to-back. The hand will be slightly bent at the time of striking the ball with the open side of the racket facing the top. After the blow, the racket walks a little in the direction of the ball, then moves left-back-down. The force of the blow in the podrezka depends on the opposite speed of the ball and the distance to the table.

The initial position is optimal for the game of the left side: the right leg is slightly pushed forward, the body is slightly turned to the right. For the blow, the hand movement, which is turned left-to-top-back and bent from the elbow, is first back and forth, at this stage the elbows are not straightened. In the process of movement, the body is slightly turned, and the center of gravity is transferred to the right leg. The angle of inclination of the racket at the time of impact can be from 0 to 90 degrees. The stronger the bottom spin at the time the opponent rotates the ball from the bottom, the sharper the bend angle. In a powerful counter-podrezka, the racket strikes the ball almost horizontally. When receiving a ball rotating from the top, the angle of inclination of the racket becomes sharper. When receiving a ball rotating strongly from the top, the podrezka should also be strong, while the direction of the racket should be almost vertical. Sometimes such extremely strongly rotated balls are perceived on the ground near the floor, since in this case the speed of rotation is significantly weakened.

In the podrezka, the force of the blow depends on the opposing speed of the ball and the distance to the table.

1. Do not raise your hand high above the shoulder when you raise your hand to strike, do not climb the racket to your right shoulder and your elbow to your body during the podrezka from the right.

2. Smooth your racket-held hand to the end and move gently but quickly. The top speed should be reached at the time of the missile strike.

3. Give the shot at the highest point in the jump from the table in front of the ball - from the side.

4. In podrezka, the end of the movement should be not on the edge, but on the front, that is, on the bottom-on the net side.

5. Change the angle of inclination of the racket depending on the direction and rotational force of the rotating ball.

6. At the time of carrying out the podrezka, the shoulder area of the hand and mainly the palms are actively moving, which helps to strongly rotate the ball from the bottom. The player who first passes the ball must have mastered the ball transfer method well-the ball must be passed in such a way that long shots are aimed and the ball does not go beyond the table, while short shots pass on a low trajectory and do not touch the net. The ball must fly at different rotations and different speeds. Only then will Conditions be created to return the opponent's shot. In pairs competitions, the player who first passes the ball must perform their actions in agreement with the pair, otherwise high results cannot be achieved in returning the opponent's shoot.

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right and left, without moving more near the table, in the possibility of making offensive and defensive shots. Various exercises can be performed for the racket to learn by hand. They can be performed independently or in the gym, at home, on the street.

1. Hit the ball. The ball is shot at the racket and hit at waist height from below in a horizontal position. It is struck alternately first on one side, then on the other, and then on the two sides.

2. Play in front of the wall. Standing at a distance of 3-4 meters in front of the wall, half-turned to the right, the ball is lightly thrown to the top and hit with the racket so that the ball touches the wall and goes back. At first, the ball can be hooked by hand, not by a racket. After the formation of the habit, the hook with the racket begins. This exercise can be complicated: let the ball thrown at the top touch the floor first, then touch the wall, then return to your racket. Playing the ball with a racket: - with one side of the racket; - with the second side of the racket; - alternately; - hit the wall; - first hit the floor and then hit the wall; - playing the ball like in badminton. Placement of players in doubles In pairs play, the rule is that the advantage is in the pair that started the game, so starting the game first gives the chance to hit.

However, the first to start a match according to the doubles match rule is awarded from right to right, in which case the advantage is on the side receiving the ball. In addition, the pair players receiving the ball agree who will be the first to receive the ball, depending on how well they master this or that style. Tactics of sharp blows after the ball is transferred. A player applying a side-up and bottom circular motion, or performing short passes with or without a turn to the right, tries to make long sharp shots pushed slightly to the right from the center line. The player is required to make sharp shots, taking into account the direction, length and type of rotation of the response ball. The player must control their power by considering the strength of the response shot. The shots should be quick and varied.

Tactics of sharp blows after the adoption of the ball. First of all, the player must be able to correctly assess the opponent's shot: in the return shot, the player striking should increase the speed of the ball's takeoff and make the direction different. It is necessary to give offensive shots mainly to the defenseless side of the opponent. In some cases, these methods can be used in reverse in order to create conditions for a blow to a partner. If a quick shot is not possible, the player can apply a quick cutting shot, but in this it is necessary to control the direction of flight of the ball so that the opponent does not respond with a quick shot, and then choose a favorable time for the attack.

Nowadays, tennis players are more often using the right-hand ball return method, rarely using a quick kick. Before hitting the ball, the player is thrown forward, lifting the shoulder area of his hand; the player's center of gravity rises to

the top. The rising ball is hit by rotating the hand inward, bringing force to the thumb, while the racket strikes the middle or top of the ball from the right side. When the racket hits the ball, the player moves imperceptibly with his palm and hand, the angle of contact of the racket with the ball does not change, about 20. Before hitting the ball, the player raises the shoulder area of their hand, the player's center of gravity rises slightly to the top, extending the hand held by the racket back and turning their body slightly to the right. The rising ball is hit when it reaches its highest point, the thumb gives the racket power, in which it will not be difficult to give a response shot, since the speed and rotation of the falling Ball will be slowed down. In order to successfully master the playing technique, it is very important to turn the ball from the bottom, as well as master the methods of making long and short strokes. After mastering the basic methods of podrezka, it is necessary that the player also learn the technique of rapid movement, which allows him to give short response shots.

A fast-moving player must control that the point of impact does not remain close to him. If the player is moving fast to the right the shot point must be on the right side of the player, if the player is moving fast to the left the shot point must be on the left side of the player. The reception of the shot according to the rule of the doubles game is carried out on the right side of the table, so the reception of the shot is easier in the doubles game than in the singles game, and the zone where the player's attention is also smaller, so it is necessary that the side receiving the Shot uses such favorable situations to take As a rule, the player receives the shot on the right side of the table, so it is very important to determine the position of the pair receiving the shot.

In practice, relatively many couples apply quick strokes or top - spins. If both players in the pair are able to perform both the left side and the right side shot, they will both have the most comfortable position; if both players in the pair perform only the right side shot, the right side should not be approached much when receiving the shot. A slight push from the centerline to the right presents a challenge in getting ready to take the opponent's shot quickly, in which the initiative can be easily lost. The player must be pushed slightly from the center line to the right, so that conditions are created to repel the shots the opponent is giving in different directions and heights. Some tennis players may have mastered the left side shot well and apply it to repel the opponent's shot. For this reason, they should approach the right-hand corner of the table muukin. In the doubles game, great importance is attached to the initiative in the reception of shots, which is applied in order to create conditions for the partner in the implementation of a powerful shot to get points. But if the technique of the striking athlete is high, it is difficult for the player receiving the shot to win points by hitting strong shots. Therefore, having the technique of using a fast shot and a fast nakat at close range allows the player to hit the right-hand corner on

the opponent's side, as well as direct the shot directed towards the opponent's body to the left. Accordingly, by changing the direction of flight of the ball, it is possible to force the opponent to move irregularly from right to left in his field and strike on his unprotected side. This, in turn, creates conditions for a large number of blows to the partner. In conclusion, the fact that a coach has a certain competency in the application of technical and tactical techniques in sports mistaking table tennis increases a high level of efficiency in athletes. The maturation of table tennis athletes and industry experts in our country has served to make our youth from this sport and the Uzbek people known to the world because of their results.

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